

Software Practitioner Survey - Explanatory Statement & Consent Form

Understanding the Influence of Cognitive Capabilities in Software Development Tasks

EXPLANATORY STATEMENT

(Software Engineering Students)

Project ID: 40008

Project title: Understanding the Influence of Cognitive Capabilities in Software Development Tasks.

The research has been approved by the Human Ethics Committee of Monash University, Australia, for five years on 20th December 2023. Reference Number:40008

Name of the Chief Investigator:

Prof John Grundy, Department of Software Systems and Cybersecurity, Faculty of Information Technology Monash University; john.grundy@monash.edu

Name of Co-Investigators:

Prof Sebastian Baltes, Faculty of Sciences, Engineering and Technology, University of Adelaide; sebastian.baltes@adelaide.edu.au

Dr Dulaji Hidellaarachchi, Department of Cybersecurity and Software Systems, School of Computing Technologies, RMIT University; dulaji.hidellaarachchi@rmit.edu.au

You are invited to take part in this study. Please read this Explanatory Statement in full before deciding whether or not to participate in this research. If you would like further information regarding any aspect of this project, you are encouraged to contact the researchers via the email addresses listed above.

What does the research involve?

In this research project, we are investigating how software engineering students' and software practitioners' personality and cognitive capabilities might influence their software development tasks. Software development is a complex and multifaceted

field that requires a combination of technical skills, problem-solving abilities, creativity and effective collaboration. As a result, individuals' cognitive capabilities and personality characteristics have garnered increasing attention in recent years. This research project seeks to delve into the interplay between these individual characteristics and how they perform software development tasks, specifically related to implementation.

Through this project, we propose to investigate the cognitive capabilities and personalities of software practitioners/ software engineering students to understand how they influence software development tasks, focusing on identifying whether there is any relationship between these characteristics and how they complete the software development tasks. Your participation is voluntary, and you will be asked to answer an online survey that includes a standard personality test, a grammatical reasoning test, and a set of questions (e.g. multiple-choice and short-answer questions) representing coding interview questions related to software development.

Upon providing the consent, the participants will be directed to the online survey, which contains four sections. The first section consists of a set of basic demographic questions, and the second section consists of the IPIP-NEO 50 test for the personality assessment, which contains 50 statements. This will take approximately 3-8 minutes to complete. The third section consists of Baddeley's grammatical reasoning test, which will take 3 minutes to complete. This test will be used to assess the cognitive capabilities of the participants in a quick and efficient way. The grammatical test consists of 64 items, and you are required to indicate your answer (true or false) for as many items as you can within three minutes. After three minutes, you will be automatically directed to the next (fourth) section of the survey. The last (fourth) section consists of a set of multiple-choice and short-answered questions that are related to data structures, code comprehension and logical puzzles, which will take around 10-15 minutes. These questions are mostly related to the coding interview questions software practitioners face during their interviews, inspired by the geeksforgeeks platform, which is built for coding challenges and interview preparations covering various domains of computer science. Altogether, the survey should take around 20-30 minutes to complete. After completing the personality assessment and grammatical reasoning test, we will provide your personality profile and the grammatical reasoning test results only at your request. We are also seeking to find some survey participants who might be willing later to participate in our next phase of the research project to find out more details about their experiences. This is optional, and more details of the next phases

will be shown upon their willingness to participate. This project is a part of Professor John Grundy's Australian Research Council Laureate Fellowship research investigating the impact of human-centric issues on software engineering.

Why were you invited for this research?

We invite you to participate in this study as you are a software engineering student (undergraduate) who is involved in software development tasks. You have been personally contacted via email invitation, or you have clicked on our survey link, which is being shared via social media such as LinkedIn, Twitter or Facebook, shared with you by one of our other participants or via Prolific. As a software engineering student who studies, understands and possesses experience in software development activities, we believe you can provide valuable insights on this topic.

PS: If you currently reside in Indonesia, you cannot participate in this study as local ethics approval (in Indonesia) has not been obtained for this study.

Consenting to participate in the project and withdrawing from the research

You have been invited to participate in this study via email, social media such as LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook or via Prolific with the information about this study and a URL to access the online survey. If you agree to participate in this study, please tick the boxes in the following consent form showing that you have read this explanatory statement, understand the purpose and method of the study, and will answer the survey.

You can withdraw your participation at any time during data collection. When submitting your online response, the data will be anonymised. Consequently, withdrawing after data has been anonymised will not be possible. If you are not willing to participate but if you are still interested in the findings of this survey, you are most welcome to contact the investigators, and they will send you a report of the findings once available.

If you are interested in participating in the next phases of the research project, you can fill in your contact details (email address), which will be asked at the end of the survey, and we will email you a statement of purpose of our next phases.

Possible benefits and risks to participants

Your participation in this study is voluntary, and no reward is given for your participation. After completing the personality assessment and the grammatical

reasoning test, your personality profile and the results of the grammatical reasoning test will be provided to you only at your request. Your valuable feedback is highly appreciated, and it is very important to understand the influence of cognitive capabilities and personality on software development tasks.

Confidentiality

Your personal data (e.g. age range, occupation) shall only be accessible to the researchers. You can fill in your email address only if you indicate that you are willing to participate in the next phases of the research or if you are willing to receive your personality profile/ the results of the grammatical reasoning test. The researchers will keep your identity confidential and will make the response anonymous. You can decide to withdraw or not to participate at any point during data collection. Once you submit your survey responses, they will be anonymised. Hence, there is no way to get back the individual responses, and at that point, your withdrawal will not be possible. After completing the personality assessment and the grammatical reasoning test, your personality profile and the results of the grammatical reasoning test will be provided to you only at your request. All the personality profiles, the results of the grammatical reasoning test and the answers to the coding interview questions will be anonymised prior to the data analysis. Any paper published as a result of the study will not identify you or your organization. The data will be stored securely. Only the researchers will have access to the data, and it will not be shared with any third party.

Storage of data

The survey data will be collected using Qualtrics and securely stored on researchers' computers. All these systems and computers are protected by password and cannot be accessed by others. Qualtrics survey data will be deleted at the survey close after downloading it to researchers' computers, and all the study data will be destroyed five years past the study.

Use of data for other purposes

The data collected from this study may be used for other studies within the next five years. Any future use of data will only occur after ethics approval has been granted. It will be done only if relevant, and in case of re-use, the data will still be in anonymised form.

Results

The results of the survey data analysis will be directed towards the next phases of

the project, as the next phases depend on the results of the survey. Moreover, the results will be published in academic conferences and/or journals for the benefit of research communities. The identity of the survey participants will not be published in any publication arising out of this research, keeping your identity confidential, and the responses you make will be published anonymously.

Complaints

Should you have any concerns or complaints about the conduct of the project, you are welcome to contact the Executive Officer, Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC):

Executive Officer

Monash University Human Research Ethics Committee (MUHREC)

Office of Research Ethics and Integrity

Room 116, Administration Building B (3D)

26 Sports Walk, Clayton Campus

Monash University VIC 3800

Tel: +61 3 9905 2025 Email: muhrec@monash.edu

Thank you

Prof John Grundy

CONSENT FORM (Software Engineering Students)

Project ID: 40008

Project Title: Understanding the influence of cognitive capabilities in software development tasks

Chief Investigator: Prof John Grundy

Co-Investigators: Dr Dulaji Hidellaarachchi, Prof Sebastian Baltes

I have been invited to take part in the Monash University research project specified above. I have read and understood the Explanatory Statement and hereby consent to participate in this project.

I consent to the following:

- I am 18 years of age or older
- I have read the Explanatory Statement and have understood the nature of the research.
- I understand that I am free to withdraw my participation at any time while taking part in the research.
- I am currently not residing in Indonesia
- I agree to answer an online survey.
- I understand that I would only receive a summary of my personality test (personality profile) and grammatical reasoning test upon my request.
- I understand that sometimes, the summary of my personality test (personality profile) may not be as pleasing as I would like it to be
- I understand that the data I provide during this research may be used by the investigators in future research projects.

Hereby, I certify that all the information above is correct. I understand that by clicking the "**I consent**" below is giving my consent to participate in this research study, and this is equivalent to signing a consent form.

Yes, I consent to participate in this survey

What is your prolific ID?

Section 01: Demographic Information

This section is intended to gather basic information of the participants for the purpose of comparing various demographics in an anonymised manner.

NOTE: We assure you that details of the participants and all other confidential information shared will be kept confidential. The participants' names and details will not be specified in any publications or reports.

How old are you?

How would you describe your gender?

- Woman
- Man
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to disclose
- Prefer to self-describe as

Do you currently reside in Indonesia?

(NOTE: Due to the absence of local ethics approval for recruitment and data collection in Indonesia, in accordance with Monash Ethics Approval guidelines, we are currently not recruiting participants who reside in Indonesia.)

- Yes
- No

Where do you live?

(Place where you are spending most of your time)

What is your current undergraduate degree program?

- Bachelor of Software Engineering
- Bachelor of Computer Science
- Bachelor of Information Technology
- Double degree with Software Engineering (Please specify):
- Other (Please specify):

Do you consider yourself a native English speaker?

- Yes
- No

If not, how would you rate your proficiency in English?

- Not proficient (You have very limited or no knowledge of English)
- Beginner (You have basic knowledge of English but struggle with understanding and communication)
- Intermediate (You can communicate in English, but with some difficulty. You may have limitations in vocabulary and grammar)
- Advanced (You are proficient in English and can communicate effectively in most situations, although you may still have occasional challenges)
- Native-like proficiency (You have the same level of fluency and language skills as a native English speaker. Your English is highly proficient, and you can communicate comfortably and confidently in all contexts)

Do you have any software engineering work experience in the industry?

- Yes, currently working
- Yes, previously worked
- No, but I have completed an internship
- No, I have not had any industry experience yet

If you are currently working, have worked, or have completed an internship, what was your job role?

What domains* are you currently working in or have worked in? Select all that apply
(*Domains - the subject area in which your current project belongs to)

- Health
- Education
- Finance
- Transport & Logistics

- Government Services
- Technology
- Manufacturing
- Others (please specify)

Which programming, scripting, and markup languages have you done extensive development work in over the past years or are familiar with?

- JavaScript
- HTML/CSS
- Python
- SQL
- TypeScript
- Java
- Bash/Shell (all shells)
- C#
- C++
- C
- PHP
- Ruby
- GO
- Rust
- Visual Basic (.Net)
- Assembly
- R
- PowerShell
- Kotlin
- Dart
- Swift
- Fortran
- GDScript
- Scala
- Objective-C
- Other (Please specify)

Section 02 - Personality Assessment

IPIP-NEO-50 Personality Test

Instructions for completing the IPIP-NEO short form:

The following pages contain phrases describing people's personality. Please use the rating scale to describe how accurately each statement describes you.

- Describe yourself as you generally are now, not as you wish to be in the future.
- Describe yourself as you see yourself in relation to other people you know of the same sex as you are and roughly your same age.
- Please read the statements carefully, and then click the circle corresponding to the statement's accuracy.
- This test consists of 50 items, and failing to answer items will return an invalid narrative report.

Note that the answer circles appear directly to the right of each question. Please make sure that the circle you are choosing corresponds to the question you are considering. If you make a mistake or change your mind, simply click the circle you wish to choose.

All responses to this inventory from all respondents are completely confidential. To ensure the confidentiality of your responses to the inventory, your responses will be anonymised when submitting, and you will be provided with your **Personality Profile only at your request.**

NOTE: This personality test is intended to gather basic personality profile of the participants. We assure details of the personality profiles will be completely anonymised and only be used to identify the relationship (if any) between personality and software development tasks.

	Very Inaccurate	Moderately Inaccurate	Neither Accurate nor Inaccurate	Moderately Accurate	Very Accurate
I am the life of the party	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel little concern for others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am always prepared	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Very Inaccurate	Moderately Inaccurate	Neither Accurate nor Inaccurate	Moderately Accurate	Very Accurate
I get stressed out easily	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have a rich vocabulary	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't talk a lot	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am interested in people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I leave my belongings around	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am relaxed most of the time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have difficulty understanding abstract ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel comfortable around people.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I insult people	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I pay attention to details	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I worry about things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have a vivid imagination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I keep in the background	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I sympathize with others' feelings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I make a mess of things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I seldom feel blue	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not interested in abstract ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I start conversations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not interested in other people's problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I get chores done right away	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am easily disturbed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have excellent ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have little to say	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Very Inaccurate	Moderately Inaccurate	Neither Accurate nor Inaccurate	Moderately Accurate	Very Accurate
I have a soft heart	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often forget to put things back in their proper place	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I get upset easily	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I do not have a good imagination	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I talk to a lot of different people at parties	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not really interested in others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I like order	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I change my mood a lot	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am quick to understand things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't like to draw attention to myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I take time out for others	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I shirk my duties	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have frequent mood swings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I use difficult words	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't mind being the center of attention	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel others' emotions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I follow a schedule	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I get irritated easily	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I spend time reflecting on things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am quiet around stranger	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I make people feel at ease	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am exacting in my work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

		Very Inaccurate	Moderately Inaccurate	Neither Accurate nor Inaccurate	Moderately Accurate	Very Accurate
I often feel blue	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am full of ideas	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Section 03 - Baddeley's Grammatical Reasoning Test

In this task, you will see a series of statements. After each statement, there are two letters. Your task is to decide whether the statement about the letters is true or false. **Respond by clicking T if you believe the statement is true or F if you believe the statement is false.**

	T (True)	F (False)
1. A follows by B - BA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. B precedes A - AB	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

For example, consider the following statement:

A is followed by B - AB

The statement is true. Look at order AB and notice that A is followed by B. You would click T for true as this is the correct answer.

Next, you will begin the task. Go as quickly as possible without making mistakes. You will have three minutes to complete as many questions as you can.

NOTE: The grammatical reasoning test is only intended to gather insights into participants' cognitive capabilities and to identify whether there is any relationship between cognitive capabilities on completing software development-related tasks. The results will be completely anonymised prior to the analysis.

Copy block

Statements

	True (T)	False (F)
B does not follow A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	True (T)	False (F)
A is not followed by B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is not preceded by B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is followed by B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A precedes B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A precedes B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is followed by A - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is preceded by A - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A does not precede B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B follows A - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is not preceded by A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A follows B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is preceded by B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is not preceded by B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is not followed by B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A follows B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is preceded by A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A follows B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B precedes A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A precedes B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is not preceded by A	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A follows B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is followed by A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
B is followed by A - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is not preceded by B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A does not precede B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A is preceded by B - BA	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
A does not follow B - AB	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

This is the end of the grammatical reasoning test!

Block 2

Section 04-I: Coding Interview Questions

NOTE: Please refrain from using ChatGPT or any other AI-generated tools to answer the following coding interview questions. We value your authentic input and insights.

Code comprehension

Consider the following pseudocode for checking balanced parentheses:

```
Declare an integer variable balance

While more input is available:
    Read a character

    If the character is '(':
        Increment balance by 1
    Else if the character is ')':
        Decrement balance by 1

    If balance < 0:
        Print "unbalanced" and exit

If balance is 0:
    Print "balanced"
Else:
    Print "unbalanced"
```

Which of the following sequences would the above code incorrectly classify as "balanced"?

- ((()))
-)()(
- ()(())

0)(00

Code comprehension

What happens when the following pseudocode is executed?

```
Set Integer value = 10
Set Integer income = 0

While (value <= 100):
    income = income + 100
    Display income

    If (income >= 1000):
        Set value = 101

End value
```

- The code executes successfully, and the value of "income" is displayed once
- The code executes successfully, and nothing is displayed
- The code executes successfully, and the value of "income" is displayed an infinite number of times
- Compilation error

Data structures

The five items, A, B, C, D and E, are pushed in a stack, one after the other, starting from A. The stack is popped four items, and each element is inserted in a queue. The two elements are deleted from the queue and pushed back on the stack. Now, one item is popped from the stack. The popped item is?

- A
- B

- C
- D

Code comprehension

You are given an array with the elements [11, 13, 21, 3] and you run the provided pseudocode that prints the next greater element for each array element. What will be the output of the pseudocode?

```
Function printNGE(arr):
  For each element, x, in arr:
    Set next to -1
    For each element, y, after x in arr:
      If x < y:
        Set next to y
        Exit the inner loop
    Print x concatenated with " -- " concatenated with next

Initialize arr with the elements [11, 13, 21, 3]
Call printNGE(arr)
```

- 11 -- 13, 13 -- 21, 21 -- -1, 3 -- -1
- 13 -- 21, 21 -- -1, 3 -- -1, 11 -- -1
- 13 -- 21, 11 -- 13, 21 -- -1, 3 -- -1
- 21 -- -1, 13 -- 21, 11 -- 13, 3 -- -1

Data structures

Suppose a circular queue of capacity $(n - 1)$ elements is implemented with an array of n elements. Assume that the insertion and deletion operations are carried out using REAR and FRONT as array index variables, respectively. Initially, REAR = FRONT = 0. The conditions to detect queue full and queue empty are?

- Full: $(\text{REAR} + 1) \bmod n == \text{FRONT}$, empty: REAR == FRONT
- Full: $(\text{REAR} + 1) \bmod n == \text{FRONT}$, empty: $(\text{FRONT} + 1) \bmod n == \text{REAR}$
- Full: REAR == FRONT, empty: $(\text{REAR} + 1) \bmod n == \text{FRONT}$
- Full: $(\text{FRONT} + 1) \bmod n == \text{REAR}$, empty: REAR == FRONT

Data Structures

Consider a hash table of size seven, with a starting index zero, and a hash function $(3x + 4) \bmod 7$. Assuming the hash table is initially empty, which of the following is the contents of the table when the sequence 1, 3, 8, 10 is inserted into the table using closed hashing?

Note that '_' denotes an empty location in the table.

- 8, _, _, _, _, _, 10
- 1, 8, 10, _, _, _, 3
- 1, _, _, _, _, _, 3
- 1, 10, 8, _, _, _, 3

Section 04-II: Logical Reasoning Questions

Number series reasoning

Find the number which will come in the place of the question mark in the given series 14, 25, 47, 91, 179, ?.

- 255
- 321
- 355
- 211

Logical Reasoning

There are six people sitting in a row facing North. A is sitting left to B but right to C. C is sitting to the immediate right of F. D is sitting left to F but right to E. Who is sitting in the middle?

- A
- C
- F
- Both B & C

Logical Reasoning/ Mathematical thinking

A man is allocated a task. He doubles the work done every day. If the man completes the task in 18 days, how many days did it take for the man to complete 25% of the task?

Block 3

Do you prefer to receive your personality profile?

- yes
 no

Do you prefer to receive your results for the grammatical reasoning test?

- yes
 no

Do you wish to participate in the next phase of our study (interview study)?

- Yes
 No

if yes, please Include your email ID

NOTE: You can fill in your email address only if you indicate that you are willing to participate in the next phases of the research or if you are willing to receive your personality profile/ the results of the grammatical reasoning test. The researchers will keep your identity confidential and will make the response anonymous

Email address:

